

Evaluating the Risk of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Using Artificial Neural Network

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ABSTRACT

To identify risk factors, neural network analysis is used to create disease prediction models, including diabetes. The goals of this study were to identify diabetes risk factors and determine their relative contribution using artificial intelligence as a mode of prediction. The current investigation was led by breaking down the dataset, as shown below. We chose a dataset from Kaggle. The diabetes dataset was from India. It has 763 female members, 497 of whom have no diabetes and 266 who have type 2 diabetes. We used neural network analysis to create mathematical models and visualize the distribution of diabetic risk factors. The significance level was set at 0.05. The current study found that the following risk factors were ranked in order of importance: Diabetes Pedigree Function, age, glucose, skin thickness, blood pressure, BMI, insulin, and number of pregnancies. When combined, neural network analysis is effective in developing mathematical models that can predict disease risk factors.

KEYWORDS: neural network analysis, artificial analysis, diabetes, risk factors, Kaggle.

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INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic, non-infectious disease [1]. T2DM can cause a variety of illnesses, including cardiovascular disease [2], stroke [3], visual impairment [4], as well as renal capacity loss [5]. Diabetes is becoming more prevalent. Diabetes affected 285 million people worldwide in 2010, compared to 422 million in 2014 [6]. This figure is expected to rise to 438 million by 2030 [7] and 592 million out of 2035 [8]. Diabetes is more prevalent in low- and moderate-income countries than in high-income countries [7]. It also accounts for a significant portion of the mortality and incapacity rates in such networks [6]. One reason for the high prevalence of diabetes in low-income countries could be a lack of diabetes knowledge and awareness [9].

Diabetes mellitus prediction is extremely important in all networks. The first step in avoiding T2DM is to recognize its risk factors. A review of the literature revealed that variables such as age [10,11], sex [10,12], family background of diabetes [11, 13], hypertension [14], stoutness [10,15], stomach weight [16], stress in the working environment or home [17,18], a stationary way of life [19,20], smoking [21], inadequate leafy

foods utilization [22], and active work [23,24] are hazard factors related with T2DM.

The Diabetes Pedigree Function, pedi, was one of the study's most intriguing features. It detailed diabetes mellitus in relatives as well as the genetic link between those relatives and the patient. This genetic influence measurement provides insight into the hereditary risk of diabetes mellitus. Based on the findings in the preceding section, it is unclear how well this function predicts the onset of diabetes [25].

STUDY OBJECTIVES

The primary goals of this study were to identify diabetes risk factors and determine their relative contribution using artificial intelligence as a mode of prediction.

METHODS

The current investigation was led by breaking down the dataset, as shown below. We chose a dataset from Kaggle. The diabetes dataset was from India. It has 763 female members, 497 of whom have no diabetes and 266 who have type 2 diabetes. We used neural network analysis to create

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mathematical models and visualize the distribution of diabetic risk factors. The significance level was set at 0.05. The dataset focused on a few risk factors, one of which is insulin. Neural network analysis predicts risk factors, autonomous factors, or covariates on the outcome, diabetes. This cycle had three layers: the input layer (covariates), the stowed away layers, and the yield layer (subordinate variable). This cycle differs from traditional measurements in

that it provides expectations that can have an impact on the reliant factors.

RESULTS

A case processing summary, as shown in table (1), was provided. A total of 540 cases (89.3%) were included in training, while 65 (10.7%) were included in testing. The number of valid cases was 605 (100%).

Table 1. Case Processing Summary

		N	Percent
Sample	Training	540	89.3%
	Testing	65	10.7%
Valid		605	100.0%
Excluded		163	
Total		768	

NETWORK INFORMATION

The model had three layers, as shown in table (2). The first (input layer) contained eight risk factors: the number of pregnancies, glucose, blood pressure, skin thickness, insulin, BMI, diabetes pedigree function, and age. The second layer(s) represented hidden layers as follows: number of

hidden layers (1), number of units in hidden layer (10), and hyperbolic tangent as the activation function. The output layer had one dependent variable (the outcome, diabetes), two units, a soft max activation function, and an error function expressed as a cross-entropy.

Table 2. Network Information

Input Layer	Factors	1	Pregnancies
		2	Glucose
		3	Blood Pressure
		4	Skin thickness
		5	Insulin
		6	BMI
		7	Diabetes Pedigree Function
		8	Age
Number of Units ^a		1069	
Hidden Layer(s)	Number of Hidden Layers		1
	Number of Units in Hidden Layer 1 ^a		10
	Activation Function		Hyperbolic tangent
Output Layer	Dependent Variables	1	outcome
	Number of Units		2
	Activation Function		Softmax
	Error Function		Cross-entropy
a. Excluding the bias unit			

MODEL SUMMARY

A model summary was provided, as shown in table (3). In the training section, approximately 31% of diabetes predictions

were incorrect. The percentage of incorrect predictions in the testing section was 29.2%.

Table 3. Model Summary

Training	Cross Entropy Error	316.633
	Percent Incorrect Predictions	31.3%
	Stopping Rule Used	1 consecutive step(s) with no decrease in error ^a

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	Training Time	0:00:16.59
Testing	Cross Entropy Error	30.760
	Percent Incorrect Predictions	29.2%
Dependent Variable: outcome		
a. Error computations are based on the testing sample.		

CLASSIFICATION

As shown in table (4), the overall percent for diabetes

prediction in the training part was 68.7%, while the overall percent for diabetes prediction in the testing part was 70.85.

Table 4. Classification

Sample	Observed	Predicted		
		.00	1.00	Percent Correct
Training	.00	325	24	93.1%
	1.00	145	46	24.1%
	Overall Percent	87.0%	13.0%	68.7%
Testing	.00	43	4	91.5%
	1.00	15	3	16.7%
	Overall Percent	89.2%	10.8%	70.8%
Dependent Variable: outcome				

INDEPENDENT VARIABLE IMPORTANCE

Diabetes Pedigree Function (100%), age (92.6%), glucose (89.6%), skin thickness (87.7%), blood pressure (84.4%),

BMI (83.3%), insulin (82.7%), and number of pregnancies (81.7%) were the most important risk factors, as shown in table (5) and figure (1).

Table 5. Independent Variable Importance

	Importance	Normalized Importance
Diabetes Pedigree Function	.142	100.0%
Age	.132	92.6%
Glucose	.128	89.6%
Skin thickness	.125	87.7%
Blood Pressure	.120	84.4%
BMI	.119	83.3%
Insulin	.118	82.7%
No of Pregnancies	.116	81.7%

Figure 1. The importance of risk factors for diabetes

DISCUSSION

According to the findings of this study, the Diabetes Pedigree Function is the most important risk factor for developing diabetes. This implies that genetic predisposition has a significant impact on the occurrence of diabetes. This was also reported in other studies in which the Diabetes Pedigree Function was identified as one of the primary causes of diabetes [26]. Age has been identified as the second most important risk factor for diabetes. This is also consistent with previous research [26]. Diabetes is more likely to develop as one gets older [26,27].

According to the findings of this study, the third most important risk factor for diabetes is blood glucose levels. Diabetes is defined and measured by glucose levels. Other datasets have identified glucose levels as an important risk factor for diabetes [26-29].

In terms of the significance of diabetic risk, skin thickness followed glucose levels. Skin thickness (the contact between the epidermis and the dermis), which is primarily determined by collagen content, is more pronounced in diabetic patients who have been diabetic for more than ten years [30]. This could be as a result of increased collagen cross-linking and decreased collagen turnover [31, 32]. Jain., et al. [33] undertook a study to assess skin and subcutaneous tissue thickness in type 2 diabetic patients, in the hope that this information will come in handy during the insulin infusion procedure. Their findings revealed that in people with a BMI of less than 23 kg/m², males had thicker skin at the arm and thigh than females (P 0.05). Males with a body mass index (BMI) of 19 to 23 kg/m² had thicker skin around the middle [34]. According to the findings, blood pressure predicted the occurrence of diabetes. This finding supported previous research that blood pressure may be a risk factor for diabetes [26, 35]. Although T2D may cause hypertension, the link between T2D and hypertension is unlikely to be causal. These findings emphasize the importance of maintaining a healthy glycemic profile in the general population, as well as BP screening and monitoring in T2D patients, particularly systolic BP [36].

According to the findings of this study, BMI is an important risk factor for diabetes. It was recently reported that pre-diagnosis BMI was related to microvascular problems in patients with incident type 2 diabetes, but weight loss was associated with a lower risk when compared to stable weight. The connections to macrovascular disease were less clear [37]. Insulin levels have been shown to be an important predictor of diabetes. We previously demonstrated that the level of insulin rises as diabetes progresses [38, 39].

According to the findings of this study, the number of pregnancies is the least important predictor of diabetes risk. Pregnancy has been linked to gestational diabetes, according to reports [40].

CONCLUSIONS

Using neural network analysis, the current study found that several important risk factors for diabetes were linked. Diabetes Pedigree Function, age, glucose, skin thickness, blood pressure, BMI, insulin, and number of pregnancies were ranked in the order of their relative importance.

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